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Rag-Fusion: A New Take on Retrieval Augmented Generation

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Abstract

Infineon has identified a need for engineers, account managers, and customers to rapidly obtain product information. This problem is traditionally addressed with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) chatbots, but in this study, I evaluated the use of the newly popularized RAG-Fusion method. RAG-Fusion combines RAG and reciprocal rank fusion (RRF) by generating multiple queries, reranking them with reciprocal scores and fusing the documents and scores. Through manually evaluating answers on accuracy, relevance, and comprehensiveness, I found that RAG-Fusion was able to provide accurate and comprehensive answers due to the generated queries contextualizing the original query from various perspectives. However, some answers strayed off topic when the generated queries' relevance to the original query is insufficient. This research marks significant progress in artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) applications and demonstrates transformations in a global and multi-industry context.

Keywords

Chatbot, Retrieval-augmented Generation, Reciprocal Rank Fusion, Natural Language Processing

Full Text: <https://airconline.com/ijnlc/V13N1/13124ijnlc03.pdf>

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Performance, Energy Consumption and Costs: A Comparative Analysis of Automatic Text Classification Approaches in the Legal Domain

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Abstract

The common practice in Machine Learning research is to evaluate the top-performing models based on their performance. However, this often leads to overlooking other crucial aspects that should be given careful consideration. In some cases, the performance differences between various approaches may be insignificant, whereas factors like production costs, energy consumption, and carbon footprint should be taken into account. Large Language Models (LLMs) are widely used in academia and industry to address NLP problems. In this study, we present a comprehensive quantitative comparison between traditional approaches (SVM-based) and more recent approaches such as LLM (BERT family models) and generative models (GPT2 and LLAMA2), using the LexGLUE benchmark. Our evaluation takes into account not only performance parameters (standard indices), but also alternative measures such as timing, energy consumption and costs, which collectively contribute to the carbon footprint. To ensure a complete analysis, we separately considered the prototyping phase (which involves model selection through training-validation-test iterations) and the in-production phases. These phases follow distinct implementation procedures and require different resources. The results indicate that simpler algorithms often achieve performance levels similar to those of complex models (LLM and generative models), consuming much less energy and requiring fewer resources. These findings suggest that companies should consider additional considerations when choosing machine learning (ML) solutions. The analysis also demonstrates that it is increasingly necessary for the scientific world to also begin to consider aspects of energy consumption in model evaluations, in order to be able to give real meaning to the results obtained using standard metrics (Precision, Recall, F1 and so on).

Keywords

NLP, text mining, green AI, green NLP, carbon footprint, energy consumption, evaluation.

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A Study on the Appropriate Size of the Mongolian General Corpus

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the appropriate size of the Mongolian general corpus. This study used the Heaps' function and Type-Token Ratio (TTR) to determine the appropriate size of the Mongolian general corpus. This study's sample corpus of 906,064 tokens comprised texts from 10 domains of newspaper politics, economy, society, culture, sports, world articles and laws, middle and high school literature textbooks, interview articles, and podcast transcripts. First, we estimated the Heaps' function with this sample corpus. Next, we observed changes in the number of types and TTR values while increasing the number of tokens by one million using the estimated Heaps' function. As a result of observation, we found that the TTR value hardly changed when the number of tokens exceeded 39~42 million. Thus, we conclude that an appropriate size for a Mongolian general corpus is 39-42 million tokens.

Keywords

Mongolian general corpus, Appropriate size of corpus, Sample corpus, Heaps' function, TTR, Type, Token.

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Evaluating BERT and ParsBERT for Analyzing Persian Advertisement Data

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Abstract

This paper discusses the impact of the Internet on modern trading and the importance of data generated from these transactions for organizations to improve their marketing efforts. The paper uses the example of Divar, an online marketplace for buying and selling products and services in Iran, and presents a competition to predict the percentage of a car sales ad that would be published on the Divar website. Since the dataset provides a rich source of Persian text data, the authors use the Hazm library, a Python library designed for processing Persian text, and two state-of-the-art language models, mBERT and ParsBERT, to analyze it. The paper's primary objective is to compare the performance of mBERT and ParsBERT on the Divar dataset. The authors provide some background on data mining, Persian language, and the two language models, examine the dataset's composition and statistical features, and provide details on their fine-tuning and training configurations for both approaches. They present the results of their analysis and highlight the strengths and weaknesses of the two language models when applied to Persian text data. The paper offers valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of working with low-resource languages such as Persian and the potential of advanced language models like BERT for analyzing such data. The paper also explains the data mining process, including steps such as data cleaning and normalization techniques. Finally, the paper discusses the types of machine learning problems, such as supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, and the pattern evaluation techniques, such as confusion matrix. Overall, the paper provides an informative overview of the use of language models and data mining techniques for analyzing text data in low-resource languages, using the example of the Divar dataset.

Keywords

Text Recognition, Persian text, NLP, mBERT, ParsBERT

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Understanding Chinese Moral Stories with Further Pre-Training

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Abstract

The goal of moral understanding is to grasp the theoretical concepts embedded in a narrative by delving beyond the concrete occurrences and dynamic personas. Specifically, the narrative is compacted into a single statement without involving any characters within the original text, necessitating a more astute language model that can comprehend connotative morality and exhibit commonsense reasoning. The “pre-training + fine-tuning” paradigm is widely embraced in neural language models. In this paper, we propose an intermediary phase to establish an improved paradigm of “pre-training + further pre-training + fine-tuning”. Further pre-training generally refers to continual learning on task-specific or domain-relevant corpora before being applied to target tasks, which aims at bridging the gap in data distribution between the phases of pre-training and fine-tuning. Our work is based on a Chinese dataset named STORAL-ZH that composes of 4k human-written story-moral pairs. Furthermore, we design a two-step process of domain-adaptive pre-training in the intermediary phase. The first step depends on a newly-collected Chinese dataset of Confucian moral culture. And the second step bases on the Chinese version of a frequently-used commonsense knowledge graph (i.e. ATOMIC) to enrich the backbone model with inferential knowledge besides morality. By comparison with several advanced models including BERT-base, RoBERTa-base and T5-base, experimental results on two understanding tasks demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed three-phase paradigm.

Keywords

Moral Understanding, Further Pre-training, Knowledge Graph, Pre-trained Language Model

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LOCATION-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS OF 2019 NIGERIA PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION USING A VOTING ENSEMBLE APPROACH

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Abstract

Nigeria president Buhari defeated his closest rival Atiku Abubakar by over 3 million votes. He was issued a Certificate of Return and was sworn in on 29 May 2019. However, there were claims of widespread hoax by the opposition. The sentiment analysis captures the opinions of the masses over social media for global events. In this paper, we use 2019 Nigeria presidential election tweets to perform sentiment analysis through the application of a voting ensemble approach (VEA) in which the predictions from multiple techniques are combined to find the best polarity of a tweet (sentence). This is to determine public views on the 2019 Nigeria Presidential elections and compare them with actual election results. Our sentiment analysis experiment is focused on location-based viewpoints where we used Twitter location data. For this experiment, we live-streamed Nigeria 2019 election tweets via Twitter API to create tweets dataset of 583816 size, pre-processed the data, and applied VEA by utilizing three different Sentiment Classifiers to obtain the choicest polarity of a given tweet. Furthermore, we segmented our tweets dataset into Nigerian states and geopolitical zones, then plotted state-wise and geopolitical-wise user sentiments towards Buhari and Atiku and their political parties. The overall objective of the use of states/geopolitical zones is to evaluate the similarity between the sentiment of location-based tweets compared to actual election results. The results reveal that whereas there are election outcomes that coincide with the sentiment expressed on Twitter social media in most cases as shown by the polarity scores of different locations, there are also some election results where our location analysis similarity test failed.

Keywords

Nigeria, Election, Sentiment Analysis, Politics, Tweets, Exploration Data Analysis, location data

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Streaming Punctuation: A Novel Punctuation Technique Leveraging Bidirectional Context for Continuous Speech Recognition

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Abstract

While speech recognition Word Error Rate (WER) has reached human parity for English, continuous speech recognition scenarios such as voice typing and meeting transcriptions still suffer from segmentation and punctuation problems, resulting from irregular pausing patterns or slow speakers. Transformer sequence tagging models are effective at capturing long bi-directional context, which is crucial for automatic punctuation. Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) production systems, however, are constrained by real-time requirements, making it hard to incorporate the right context when making punctuation decisions. Context within the segments produced by ASR decoders can be helpful but limiting in overall punctuation performance for a continuous speech session. In this paper, we propose a streaming approach for punctuation or re-punctuation of ASR output using dynamic decoding windows and measure its impact on punctuation and segmentation accuracy across scenarios. The new system tackles over-segmentation issues, improving segmentation F0.5-score by 13.9%. Streaming punctuation achieves an average BLEU score improvement of 0.66 for the downstream task of Machine Translation (MT).

Keywords

automatic punctuation, automatic speech recognition, re-punctuation, speech segmentation.

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A Robust Three-Stage Hybrid Framework for English to Bangla Transliteration

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Abstract

Phonetic typing using the English alphabet has become widely popular nowadays for social media and chat services. As a result, a text containing various English and Bangla words and phrases has become increasingly common. Existing transliteration tools display poor performance for such texts. This paper proposes a robust Three-stage Hybrid Transliteration (THT) framework that can transliterate both English words and phonetic typed Bangla words satisfactorily. This is achieved by adopting a hybrid approach of dictionary-based and rule-based techniques. Experimental results confirm superiority of THT as it significantly outperforms the benchmark transliteration tool.

Keywords

Transliteration framework, phonetic typing, English to Bangla, hybrid framework, THT.

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Analyzing Architectures for Neural Machine Translation using Low Computational Resources

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Abstract

With the recent developments in the field of Natural Language Processing, there has been a rise in the use of different architectures for Neural Machine Translation. Transformer architectures are used to achieve state-of-the-art accuracy, but they are very computationally expensive to train. Everyone cannot have such setups consisting of high-end GPUs and other resources. We train our models on low computational resources and investigate the results. As expected, transformers outperformed other architectures, but there were some surprising results. Transformers consisting of more encoders and decoders took more time to train but had fewer BLEU scores. LSTM performed well in the experiment and took comparatively less time to train than transformers, making it suitable to use in situations having time constraints.

Keywords

Machine Translation, Indic Languages, Natural Language Processing.

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Developing Products Update-Alert System for E-Commerce Websites Users using Html Data and Web Scraping Technique

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Abstract

Websites are regarded as domains of limitless information which anyone and everyone can access. The new trend of technology has shaped the way we do and manage our businesses. Today, advancements in Internet technology has given rise to the proliferation of e-commerce websites. This, in turn made the activities and lifestyles of marketers/vendors, retailers and consumers (collectively regarded as users in this paper) easier as it provides convenient platforms to sale/order items through the internet. Unfortunately, these desirable benefits are not without drawbacks as these platforms require that the users spend a lot of time and efforts searching for best product deals, products updates and offers on ecommerce websites. Furthermore, they need to filter and compare search results by themselves which takes a lot of time and there are chances of ambiguous results. In this paper, we applied web crawling and scraping methods on an e-commerce website to obtain HTML data for identifying products updates based on the current time. These HTML data are preprocessed to extract details of the products such as name, price, post date and time, etc. to serve as useful information for users.

Keywords

NATURAL LANGUAGE PREPROCESSING (NLP), E-COMMERCE, E-RETAIL, HTML, DATA, Web, Webscraping

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